

EV Hybrid Battery with Integrated Multilevel Neutral-Point-Clamped Interfacing and Lossless Intermodule State-of-Charge Balancing

Gabriel Garcia-Rojas¹ (Graduate Student Member, IEEE), Sergio Busquets-Monge¹ (Senior Member, IEEE), Àlber Filbà-Martínez², Turev Sarikurt³, Salvador Alepuz⁴ (Senior Member, IEEE), and Josep Bordonau¹ (Member, IEEE)

¹Electronic Engineering Department, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, 08028 Spain

²Catalonia Energy Research Institute, Sant Adrià del Besòs, 08930 Spain

³Rail Transport Technologies Institute, Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey, Kocaeli, 41400 Turkey

⁴Tecnocampus Mataró-Maresme, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Mataró, 08302 Spain

Corresponding author: Gabriel Garcia-Rojas (e-mail: gabriel.garcia.rojas@upc.edu).

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 963646. The content of this manuscript only reflects the view of its authors. The European Commission and its agency are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ABSTRACT The battery is at the heart of the electric vehicle and determines many of its key performance features. Therefore, an optimized design of the battery is critical. On one hand, the design of batteries based on a single battery cell leads in many cases to oversized batteries in terms of energy or power, due to the diversity of requirements of the different electric vehicles. On the other hand, the use of a custom cell for each vehicle, optimized for its particular requirements, is not economically viable. Instead, hybrid batteries, combining only two battery cell chemistries, with distinct particular strengths, such as high specific energy or high specific power, offer an opportunity to cover a wide range of vehicle battery specifications while avoiding oversizing and a dispersion in the cells to be employed. This work introduces a novel hybrid battery configuration, where the interfacing between the two sets of cells is accomplished through a bidirectional multilevel neutral-point-clamped dc-dc converter. The novel topology is presented and a suitable power converter modulation and control strategy is developed. The feasibility and benefits of such configuration are demonstrated and illustrated. Particularly, the proposed battery system allows the balancing of the state-of-charge (SoC) of the battery modules within both sets of battery banks, which is achieved without introducing additional power losses. The SoC balancing is simply accomplished through the regulation of the power to be extracted/delivered from/to each battery module by the power converter during regular battery discharging and charging operations. The converter features enough regulation margin to correct substantial SoC imbalances. Overall, the proposed approach enables a modular and scalable design of the energy storage system for a wide range of electric vehicles, from only two different standard battery modules and a standard power semiconductor device, while optimizing the battery size for any given battery power and energy specification. Simulation and experimental results are provided in the case of a three-level internal battery interfacing to verify the good performance of the proposed novel hybrid battery configuration, modulation, and control.

INDEX TERMS Hybrid battery, modulation, multilevel, neutral-point-clamped, state-of-charge balancing.

NOMENCLATURE

C_{bk} Tank dc-blocking capacitor value.

E_{bat}^* Energy requirement for the battery.

f_s Switching frequency.

i_{2a} Current flowing through the dc-link node 2 of side A.

I_{2a} Average current flowing through the dc-link node 2 of side A.

i_{A1}, i_{A2} Currents flowing through the battery modules A1 and A2 and their parallel capacitors, respectively.

I_{A1}, I_{A2}	Average currents flowing through the battery modules A1, A2 and their parallel capacitors, respectively.
i_T	Tank current.
I_T	RMS value of the tank current.
$i_{T,1}$	Fundamental component of the tank current.
$i_{T,1}^p$	In-phase and component of $i_{T,1}$.
$i_{T,1}^q$	In-quadrature component of $i_{T,1}$.
k_a, k_b	Control effort of the state-of-charge closed-loop control of sides A and B, respectively.
L_T	Tank inductance.
m_a, m_b	Modulation index of sides A and B, respectively.
n_a, n_b	Number of levels of sides A and B, respectively.
P_a, P_b	Active power delivered by sides A and B, respectively.
P_{bat}^*	Power requirement for the battery.
Q_a, Q_b	Reactive power delivered by sides A and B, respectively.
$q(t)$	Stored battery module charge at time t .
Q_{nom}	Nominal battery module capacity.
R_L	Load resistance.
R_T	Tank resistance.
s_a, s_b	NPC-leg connection state of sides A and B, respectively.
sp_a, sp_b	Sign of the active power delivered by sides A and B, respectively.
sq_a, sq_b	Sign of the reactive power delivered by sides A and B, respectively.
sc_{A1}, sc_{A2}	State of charge of battery modules A1 and A2, respectively.
sc_{B1}, sc_{B2}	State of charge of battery modules B1 and B2, respectively.
$scimb_A, scimb_B$	State of charge imbalance of sides A and B, respectively.
$scimb_A^*, scimb_B^*$	Command for the state of charge imbalance of sides A and B, respectively.
v_a, v_b	Synthesized instantaneous output voltage of sides A and B, respectively.
V_a, V_b	RMS value of the fundamental component of v_a and v_b , respectively.
V_{A1}, V_{A2}	A1 and A2 battery module voltages, respectively.
V_{dca}, V_{dcb}	Total dc voltage of sides A and B, respectively.
v_T	Tank circuit voltage.
α_j	Modulation pattern switching angles, where $j = a, b, c, d$.
β	Phase shift of the fundamental component of the current flowing through the tank, $I_{T,1}$, with respect to the fundamental output voltage of side B.
θ_a, θ_b	Modulation angle of sides A and B, respectively.
φ	Phase shift of the fundamental output voltage of side-A, with respect to the fundamental output voltage of side B.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric vehicles (EVs) are already playing an essential role in the transition toward a low-carbon global economy. Supported by the various initiatives of countries and institutions [1], [2], it is anticipated that the number of EVs will continue to grow in the coming years.

Similar to internal combustion engine vehicles, there is a wide variety of EVs, ranging from small commuter cars to heavy-duty commercial vehicles. These EVs can greatly differ in their battery requirements, including energy, power [3], charging time [4], regenerative braking capacity, cost, and lifespan. In addition, these EV battery requirements must be met under different operating conditions, such as varying states-of-charge (SoC) and extreme temperatures. Since it is not viable to build the battery for each vehicle around an optimal battery cell designed specifically for this vehicle, the EV battery pack designs based on a single standard battery cell end up often being oversized in some aspects [5], [6].

Instead, a hybrid battery energy storage system (HBESS) is built from a combination of two types of battery cells, each one featuring different chemistries, with the intention of finding a more optimal solution. Each battery cell technology features a particular strength, such as high specific energy or high specific power, and the hybrid battery takes advantage of this combination of strengths to meet all the system requirements with less battery volume and weight, and extending battery life. This is illustrated in the following through a simple example.

Let us assume that in the design of a battery, specific energy (SE) and specific power (SP) are of utmost importance. Let us also assume that only two cell types are available, depicted in Fig. 1. Cell type A is optimized to store energy and in contrast presents a moderate specific power. Cell type B is optimized to provide power but presents a moderate specific energy.

Fig. 2 illustrates the energy (E) and power (P) achieved with 1 kg of each cell. Thus, the lengths of the blue and red lines, which are in this example approximately equal, correspond to one kg of each cell type. When a high-energy low-power

FIGURE 1. Characteristics of cell A and cell B.

FIGURE 2. Power and energy of 1kg of cell A and cell B.

battery is to be designed, with the requirements depicted by point ① in Fig. 3(a), where E_{bat}^* represents the minimum required battery energy and P_{bat}^* represents the minimum required battery power, then it will be optimal to use cell type A. As can be observed in Fig. 3(a), using cell type A leads to a lower battery weight, since the blue line is shorter than the red line. Conversely, when a high-power low-energy battery is to be designed, with the requirements depicted by point ②, the optimal cell to use will be cell B, as shown in Fig. 3(b).

However, when a battery with a more balanced energy and power requirements is needed, such as the one represented by point ③ in Fig. 3(c), both cell types, if used alone, lead to a heavy battery, as depicted in Fig. 3(c). In this case, instead, a combination of both cells allows to fulfill the battery requirements with a much lower overall weight, as shown in Fig. 3(d). Therefore, hybrid batteries offer the possibility of obtaining batteries with different ratios of energy and power in an optimal way. From a different perspective, hybridization is equivalent to employing a virtual cell with characteristics at any selected intermediate point along the straight line joining cell A and cell B in Fig. 1.

Some examples in the literature propose the hybridization of different energy storage systems, at cell level [7] and at system level [6], [8], [9], [10]. From the architectural point of view, two options are considered: passive and active systems. Passive systems do not contain any power converter to interface the storage elements, thereby lowering the total

system cost but imposing significant restrictions, such as cell voltage curve compatibility [11], [12]. Alternatively, in active systems, the inclusion of a power converter interface increases the degrees of freedom of the system. The interface of the storage elements has been reported to be implemented through a single two-level power converter [9], [13], [14], [15], [16], a converter for each element [3], [17], [18], a three-level three-phase neutral-point-clamped (NPC) dc-ac converter [19], a cascaded H-bridge converter (CHB) [10], [20], [21], [22], [23], or with other converters [24], [25], [26].

The use of multilevel converters fed by several battery modules allows controlling the current of each battery module as a function of its individual SoC, which maximizes the energy delivered by the full battery pack [23], [27]. Therefore, these converters are well suited for the interfacing in active hybrid battery systems. However, their application has not been fully explored outside the CHB-based HBESS [10], [20], [21], [22], [23] and the configuration of hybrid batteries using other multilevel topologies still requires further investigation. In order to cover this gap, this paper, developed under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Helios project [28], with a consortium of eighteen partners, proposes a novel active hybrid battery configuration employing a novel NPC multilevel converter as the interface between the two battery banks, with one of the banks being directly connected to the load.

Compared to existing state-of-the-art HBESS configurations, the proposed design leverages the advantages of NPC converter topologies, such as the potential for the highest power density among multilevel topologies and the reduced number of passive components. When the converter legs are implemented with the active NPC topology, all semiconductor devices feature the same voltage rating [29]. Compared to HBESS topologies employing 2-level converters, the proposed system features intermodule non-dissipative SoC balancing capability. Compared to CHB converter-based topologies, where each battery module must be isolated [10], the proposed HBESS configuration interconnects the battery modules in series. This point is particularly important in EV applications, where space constraints and high power density requirements tend to favor topologies with reduced isolation and clearance distances.

FIGURE 3. Different battery designs meeting the battery energy and power specifications (E_{bat}^* , P_{bat}^*). (a) High-energy battery. (b) High-power battery. (c) Battery with balanced power and energy specification. (d) Hybrid battery with balanced power and energy specification.

Furthermore, the proposed circuit topology is simple and only requires two NPC legs, an inductor and a capacitor, thereby facilitating its implementation and scalability employing standard battery modules and a standard semiconductor device. Finally, it is assumed that the battery bank which directly connects to the load employs high-power battery cells, while the other side utilizes high-energy battery cells. The power exchanged between both battery banks through the converter is limited by the high-energy lower-power battery bank. Thus, the converter power rating is not required to be sized according to the total power of the HBESS.

These characteristics make the implementation of active HBESS particularly relevant for the standardization of vehicle design and manufacturing, regardless of the battery cell technologies employed. As depicted in Fig. 1, the proposed approach, by using only two different battery cell chemistries, allows the conception of a virtual battery cell with intermediate performance, which can be easily customized with tailored power and range, and with relevant battery weight reduction. EVs are subjected to frequent strong accelerations and decelerations, requiring a significant amount of power during this transient operation. High-power battery cells handle this kind of load more efficiently than high-energy battery cells, generating less heat and providing a longer life cycle [30]. On the other hand, high-energy battery cells can provide increased range more efficiently.

The main contributions of this paper are as follows.

- 1) The conception of the topology, basic operation and power flow control of a novel n -level active HBESS topology.
- 2) The development of a battery intermodule SoC balance control through a modification of the converter modulation and without introducing additional losses; i.e., the SoC balance itself presents a lossless operation.
- 3) The verification of the suitability of the proposed topology and control through simulation and experiments.

The manuscript is organized as follows. Section II proposes the NPC-based active HBESS topology and operating principle. Section III presents the proposed modulation and charge balancing control. Sections IV and V present simulation and experimental results to verify the good performance of the aforementioned systems, respectively. Finally, Section VI outlines the conclusions.

II. PROPOSED HBESS TOPOLOGY AND OPERATING PRINCIPLE

The proposed generalized HBESS topology is presented in Fig. 4. It is formed by two battery banks. Battery bank A consists of n_a-1 modules connected in series and battery bank B consists of n_b-1 modules connected in series, each one coupled with a parallel capacitor C . The load is directly fed from battery bank B, while battery bank A is connected to battery bank B through a power electronics interfacing consisting of two NPC legs and a tank circuit. The NPC legs

are here modeled as single-pole multiple-throw switches, with n_a throws on side A and n_b throws on side B. Fig. 5 shows some possible implementations of such NPC legs for the particular case of three levels. The tank circuit consists of an inductor L_T and a capacitor C_{bk} . The capacitor C_{bk} blocks the dc component of the tank voltage v_T . Thus, only ac current flows through the tank in steady state. The return path for the tank current i_T is indicated by the ground symbols on the middle dc-link point in both battery banks, as shown in Fig. 4. However, notice that the return path can be connected to any dc-link point on both sides, and these two dc-link points can differ. The location of these points only affects the value of the dc voltage on C_{bk} . This feature enables different hybrid battery pack configuration options, as those illustrated in Fig. 6. Fig. 4 and Fig. 6(a) correspond to the parallel configuration, where the return path would be typically connected to an analogous dc-link point on both sides. Instead, Fig. 6(b) corresponds to a series connection, where the return path is connected to the bottom dc-link point in side A and to the top dc-link point in battery bank B. This last configuration provides higher load voltage. The discussion about the merits of each configuration is beyond the scope of the present manuscript. This work is developed with the parallel configuration of Fig. 4 and Fig. 6(a).

The power flow between side A and B is controlled by means of the voltages v_a and v_b generated by the NPC legs, with fundamental components of rms value V_a and V_b , respectively, phase-shifted φ degrees. The corresponding phasors are represented in Fig. 7. The tank rms voltage V_T , computed as the difference between V_a and V_b , is essentially applied over the inductor impedance, generating the tank current with rms value I_T and phase β .

The synthesized voltages and the tank current define the active and reactive power exchanged between A and B. The active power transferred from A to B is

$$P_a = -P_b = V_a \cdot I_T \cdot \cos(\beta - \varphi) = \frac{V_a \cdot V_b \cdot \sin(\varphi)}{\omega L}, \quad (1)$$

while the reactive power delivered from side A can be computed as

$$Q_a = V_a \cdot I_T \cdot \sin(\beta - \varphi) = \frac{V_a^2 - V_a V_b \cdot \cos(\varphi)}{\omega L}, \quad (2)$$

and the reactive power from side B can be expressed as

$$Q_b = -V_b \cdot I_T \cdot \sin(\beta) = -\frac{V_b^2 - V_b V_a \cdot \cos(\varphi)}{\omega L}. \quad (3)$$

The reactive power represents the energy that flows back and forth between the batteries and the tank without net energy transfer.

Fig. 8 shows the normalized active and reactive power as a function of φ , for the particular case $V_a = V_b$. For a given amplitude V_a and V_b , the active power can be regulated adjusting the phase shift φ between $-\pi/2$ and $\pi/2$. Pure reactive power with no active power can be exchanged if $V_a \neq V_b$ and $\varphi = 0$, or if $\varphi = \pi$.

FIGURE 4. Proposed generalized HBESS topology with n_a levels on battery side A and n_b levels on battery side B.

FIGURE 5. Some examples of NPC leg topologies. (a) Three levels, diode clamped. (b) Three levels, active clamped. (c) Three levels, T-type.

FIGURE 6. Two possible hybrid battery pack configurations depending on the connection of the tank current return path. (a) Parallel. (b) Series.

FIGURE 7. Phasor diagram illustrating the system operating principle.

The active power flow discussed in this section is illustrated in Fig. 9 for the particular case of three levels on both battery sides. The multilevel dc-dc converter extracts active power P_{A1} and P_{A2} from the A-side battery modules and delivers the aggregated power $P_a = P_{A1} + P_{A2}$ to the B-side: P_{X1} towards module B1 and P_{X2} towards module B2. Finally, a load consuming P_L is fed from the B side battery bank. In particular, Fig. 9 illustrates the case where $P_{A1} = P_{A2} = P_{X1} = P_{X2} = P_L/4$, which corresponds to an operating mode under balanced contribution of power to the load from each battery bank and balanced SoC conditions. In general, with the proposed operation principle, the system can adjust the amount of energy transferred from side-A battery bank to side B.

The operation of the NPC legs demands high-frequency pulsating currents on the battery-capacitor pairs. The purpose of the parallel capacitors is to provide a low-impedance path for these high-frequency components, so that the battery modules supply only the dc component. However, there is a

FIGURE 8. Normalized active and reactive power as a function of ϕ , for $V_a = V_b$.

design tradeoff in the selection of this capacitance. A minimum capacitance value is necessary to provide the converter leg commutation currents through a path with a low leakage inductance. As the capacitance is increased above this minimum value, the high-frequency current ripple through the battery modules is reduced, at the expense of increasing the capacitor size. Given this, to select a suitable design tradeoff solution, it is important to assess the potential negative impact of a high-frequency current ripple on a battery module. First, this current ripple contributes to increase the battery rms current for a given power delivery, leading to an increase in the battery losses due to the Joule effect, which in turn raises the cell temperature and accelerates aging [31], [32]. According to this, several studies have proposed alternatives to minimize the battery rms current on multilevel topologies [33], [34]. However, experimental studies have found no evidence to demonstrate a measurable increase in aging caused by high-frequency current ripple on different cell chemistries. M. Uno and K. Tanaka found no significant difference in aging of LiNiCoO₂/graphite cells when exposed to high-frequency sinusoidal currents, and only lower frequencies caused accelerated aging [35]. M. J. Brand *et al.* reported analogous findings on NiMnCoO₂/graphite cells [36]. More recently, A. Ghassemi *et al.* also concluded that high-frequency ac currents superimposed on a dc offset do not contribute to ageing on LiFePO₄ cells [37]. One explanation for this phenomenon may be that the high-frequency currents flow through the double-layer capacitance of the cells, similar in structure and behavior to a supercapacitor, preventing any charge-transfer process, although they can cause a minor increase in temperature. F. Chang *et al.* [38], stated that the necessary condition for a current ripple to cause battery degradation is that it should feature low frequency and that it should cause the battery current to change direction. This thesis is further reinforced by several studies showing

FIGURE 9. Power flow across a HBESS with two battery modules on each side ($n_a = n_b = 3$) feeding a load, under balanced contribution of power to the load from each battery bank and balanced SoC conditions.

increased aging when this condition is met [35], [39]. Additionally, the cell temperature has to be significantly affected. When the cell temperature is tightly controlled, the authors in [40] were not able to find any measurable difference in capacity fade or increase in internal resistance, in this case for LiNiMnCoO₂/graphite cells.

Fig. 10 shows an example profile of the A1 battery module current, i_{A1} , in the absence of a parallel capacitor, during a discharge process of battery A1, for the system proposed in Fig. 4 at three levels, side-A modulation index $m_a = 0.9$, side-B modulation index $m_b = 0.9$, and phase-shift $\varphi = 45^\circ$. Under these operating conditions, the active power is much higher than the reactive power, and it can be observed that the current does not change direction at any instant of time. Furthermore, the current profile for any value of the modulation index and phase-shift only contains high frequency harmonics. The frequency spectrum is shown in Fig. 11. Even though the current may change direction when the system operates with large reactive values, the conditions reported in [38] are not met and only a small increase in temperature is expected. Additionally, the loss of total battery bank capacity due to different module aging (possibly generated by different temperature stress) can be significantly minimized thanks to an intermodule SoC balancing control [38]. During charging, the potential negative effects are even less concerning, as several authors have found that pulse charging can reduce ageing compared to constant current charging [37], [41], [42], [43], [44].

FIGURE 10. Example current profile of battery A1 without parallel capacitor, under a three-level system ($n_a = n_b = 3$), $m_a = 0.9$, $m_b = 0.9$, $\varphi = 45^\circ$.

III. MODULATION AND SoC BALANCING CONTROL

This section presents the NPC leg modulation and the battery intermodule SoC balancing. To help the reader understand the proposed operation, this work has been developed with the simplest case, using a three-level NPC leg on both sides. However, it is important to highlight that the method described here can be properly extended to any number of levels. Fig. 12 presents this simple case derived from the general topology, with two series-connected battery modules per side interfaced through a three-level converter, which is here implemented with the active NPC topology. The figure provides additional information necessary for the simulation and experimental sections, that will be detailed in sections IV and V.

For the sake of simplicity, the analysis is carried out on side A in Fig. 12, although the analysis on side B is fully equivalent.

Fig. 13 presents the voltage pattern v_a to be generated through the operation of the NPC leg. Typically, $\alpha_a = \alpha_b = \alpha_c = \alpha_d = \alpha$ to force quarter-wave symmetry, eliminating even order harmonics and providing waveform simplicity. In this case, the rms value of the fundamental component depends on α as follows

$$V_a = \frac{\sqrt{2}V_{dca}}{\pi} \cdot \sin(\alpha), \quad (4)$$

where $V_{dca} = V_{A1} + V_{A2}$ is the total side-A dc-link voltage. Likewise, the modulation index can then be defined as

$$m_a = \frac{V_a}{V_{dca}/\sqrt{6}} = \frac{2\sqrt{3}}{\pi} \cdot \sin(\alpha), \quad (5)$$

where the modulation index varies from 0 to $2\sqrt{3}/\pi \approx 1.1$ for α varying from 0 to $\pi/2$.

FIGURE 11. Frequency spectrum of the current delivered by battery A1 without a parallel capacitor, under a three-level system ($n_a = n_b = 3$), $m_a = 0.9$, $m_b = 0.9$, $\varphi = 45^\circ$.

FIGURE 12. HBESS circuit schematic with three levels on battery side A and three levels on battery side B ($n_a = n_b = 3$). Both converter legs are implemented with the active NPC topology. Both the simulations and the hardware prototype follow this design.

Let us now analyze the effect of the NPC leg operation on the battery current balance. From Fig. 12, applying Kirchhoff current law at dc-link node 2

$$i_{2a} - i_T = i_{A1} - i_{A2}, \quad (6)$$

where i_{Ax} ($x \in \{1, 2\}$) is the addition of the current that flows through the battery ($i_{Ax,bat}$) and the capacitor ($i_{Ax,cap}$).

On average over the switching cycle

$$I_{2a} = I_{A1} - I_{A2}, \quad (7)$$

which indicates that the average neutral-point current I_{2a} is responsible for the imbalance of the two battery currents; i.e., forcing $I_{2a} = 0$ keeps the two battery currents balanced. Fig. 13 includes the plot of the fundamental component of the tank current $i_{T,1} = i^{p_{T,1}} + i^{q_{T,1}}$, decomposed into a component in phase with the fundamental component of v_a ($i^{p_{T,1}}$, responsible for the active power transfer) and a component in quadrature ($i^{q_{T,1}}$, responsible for the reactive power transfer). All the other harmonics of i_T are neglected.

In Fig. 13, with $\alpha_a = \alpha_b = \alpha_c = \alpha_d = \alpha$, the blue and green solid areas, representing the charge drawn from (positive areas) or injected into (negative areas) the neutral point, cancel out in both $i^{p_{T,1}}$ and $i^{q_{T,1}}$. This results in $I_{2a} = 0$ and it means that both battery modules feature the same current, ideal for a balanced charging and discharging of these two battery modules.

However, it can be useful to introduce an imbalance in the battery currents. For instance, this imbalance can be applied to equalize the two battery modules SoCs when they are unequal. This can be done by modifying the width and/or position of the positive and negative pulses of v_a in correlation with $i^{p_{T,1}}$ and/or $i^{q_{T,1}}$. An example is depicted in Fig. 14(a), where the width of the positive and negative pulses is reduced and increased, respectively. The green areas still cancel out in $i^{q_{T,1}}$, but they no longer cancel out in $i^{p_{T,1}}$, resulting in a positive average neutral-point current $I_{2a} > 0$ and imbalanced battery module currents $I_{A1} > I_{A2}$.

In Fig. 14(b), the position of the positive and negative pulses is moved right and left, respectively. The blue areas still cancel out in $i^{p_{T,1}}$, but they no longer cancel out in $i^{q_{T,1}}$, introducing an $I_{2a} > 0$ that will force $I_{A1} > I_{A2}$.

That is, the imbalance of the battery currents can be controlled through the tank current associated to the active and reactive power being transferred, by modifying the width and/or position of the positive and negative pulses of v_a .

Fig. 15 shows a proper closed-loop control diagram based on this principle, where $scimb_A = sc_{A1} - sc_{A2}$ is the imbalance between the SoC of battery module 1 and battery module 2 of side A, $sc(t) = q(t)/Q_{nom}$, $q(t)$ is the stored battery module charge at time t , Q_{nom} is its nominal capacity, $scimb_A^*$ is the command for the SoC imbalance of side A, and $s_a(t) \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ is a variable that indicates the dc-link point where the NPC leg is connected at each point in time. A proportional gain in the controller $G_c(s)$ is sufficient for a successful system implementation.

To determine s_a in the modulator block of Fig. 15, it is required to first determine the switching angles with

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_a &= \alpha \cdot [1 + k_a \cdot (sp_a + sq_a)] \\ \alpha_b &= \alpha \cdot [1 + k_a \cdot (sp_a - sq_a)] \\ \alpha_c &= \alpha \cdot [1 + k_a \cdot (-sp_a - sq_a)] \\ \alpha_d &= \alpha \cdot [1 + k_a \cdot (-sp_a + sq_a)] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where α can be obtained from (5), sp_a is the sign of the active power delivered by side A (+1 if $i^{p_{T,1}}$ is as depicted in Fig. 13 and -1 if it is phase-shifted 180 degrees), sq_a is the sign of the reactive power (+1 if $i^{q_{T,1}}$ is as depicted in Fig. 13 and -1 if it is phase-shifted 180 degrees), and k_a is the control effort variable.

If it is desired to restrict the control action only to the active power, sq_a has to be set to zero in (8). Alternatively, if it is desired to restrict the control action only to the reactive power, sp_a has to be set to zero in (8). The value of the control effort variable k_a may need to be restricted to prevent the switching angles from going outside the feasible range $[0, \pi/2]$.

FIGURE 13. Three-level modulation pattern [45].

FIGURE 14. Control action to correct imbalance. (a) Through the in-phase current component (active power). (b) Through the in-quadrature current component (reactive power).

Fig. 16 illustrates the power flow in the HBESS under this SoC balancing control in action. It is assumed that $scimb_A < 0$ and $scimb_B > 0$. The power delivered from side-A battery modules, P_{A1} and P_{A2} , is unbalanced due to the control action on the converter side-A modulation. Similarly, the energy delivered from the converter to side-B battery modules, P_{X1} and P_{X2} , is also unbalanced due to the control action on the converter side-B modulation. The SoCs of all battery modules are regulated simply through the control of the individual power delivered/received by each battery module.

It is very relevant to highlight that since the proposed charge balancing control does not introduce any additional commutations and since there is no charge transfer among modules of the same battery bank—all the charge transferred is directly delivered from one battery bank to the other—, no additional losses are introduced due to this charge balancing control. Therefore, the system can balance each individual battery module SoC in a lossless manner.

Fig. 17 illustrates this SoC lossless balancing control in comparison to the typical passive balancing control and active balancing controls. Two battery modules connected in series are considered (Bat1 and Bat2). Their charge/energy is represented by a solid bar. The energy of the two battery modules is initially unbalanced. In Fig. 17(a), a passive balancing circuit burns the excess energy of Bat1 to achieve SoC balance. This excess energy is therefore lost. In Fig. 17(b), an active balancing circuit delivers part of the excess energy of Bat1 to Bat2 to achieve SoC balance. However, the active balancing circuits incur in some losses. Therefore, part of the energy is lost in a power transfer exclusively undertaken to achieve SoC balance. Finally, in Fig. 17(c), the balancing is simply achieved by properly adjusting the power delivered by Bat1 and Bat2 to the load, or alternatively adjusting the power received by Bat1 and Bat2 from a source. This power transfer will obviously incur in some losses, but since the same overall power transfer has to be produced to power the load or to charge the battery bank, these losses would occur anyway, and cannot be attributed to the SoC balancing process itself. Thus, this third balancing technique is regarded as being lossless. In addition, another advantage is that it does not require a specific balancing circuit.

FIGURE 15. Closed-loop control block diagram of a HBESS with three levels on battery side A and three levels on battery side B ($n_a = n_b = 3$).

FIGURE 16. Power flow across a HBESS with two battery modules on each side ($n_a = n_b = 3$) feeding a load, under balanced contribution of power to the load from each battery bank and unbalanced SoC conditions.

FIGURE 17. Classification of SoC balancing techniques. (a) Passive balancing. (b) Active balancing. (c) Lossless balancing.

TABLE 1. BATTERY MODULE

Parameter	Value
Cell model	Samsung ICR18650-22P
Cell chemistry	LiNiMnCoO ₂ (NMC)
Module configuration	13S2P
Nominal voltage, V_{nom}	47 V
Charging cut-off voltage, V_{max}	55 V
Discharging cut-off voltage, V_{min}	38 V
Nominal capacity, Q_{nom}	4.3 Ah @ 0.2C discharge rate
Nominal stored energy, E_{nom}	202 Wh @ 0.2C discharge rate

TABLE 2. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Battery bank	
$C_{A1} = C_{A2} = 1.09 \text{ mF}$	$C_{B1} = C_{B2} = 1.09 \text{ mF}$
Tank	
$C_{bk} = 30 \text{ }\mu\text{F}$	$R_T = 10 \text{ m}\Omega$
$L_T = 94 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$	
Load	
$R_L = 20 \text{ }\Omega$	
NPC leg modulation and control	
$m_a = 0.9$	$f_s = 10 \text{ kHz}$
$m_b = 0.9$	$G_c(s) = 20$
$\varphi = \pi/2$	

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A switching model and a switching-cycle-averaged model of the system depicted in Fig. 12 have been implemented in MATLAB-Simulink to analyze the performance of the proposed HBESS system. For convenience and simplicity, the same battery module is used in sides A and B. The selected battery module model has been obtained from [27]. The converter legs are modeled as ideal single-pole multiple-throw switches. The load is modeled as a resistor with value R_L . The system parameters and operating conditions presented in Tables 1 and 2 are the same for both the simulations and the experimental tests.

The system operates with two battery modules and one three-level leg on each side ($n_a = n_b = 3$). For the sake of simplicity and due to symmetry, only side A variables are reported.

In the first test, the switching model is employed to verify the working principle in detail, as shown in Fig. 18 under open-loop control; i.e., forcing $k_a = 0$. Notice that k_a is the control effort variable of side A. The synthesized voltages v_a and v_b are phase shifted by 90° , leading to an operation with in-phase and in-quadrature power exchange, verified by the phase shift of the tank current i_T with respect to v_a and v_b . A balanced operation is achieved even when operating in open loop control, as the discontinuous lines representing the average value of the battery module currents $i_{A2, \text{bat}}$ and $i_{A1, \text{bat}}$ have the same value, 2.56 A.

In Fig. 19(a), the closed-loop control is activated but restricted to operate only with the active power ($sq_a = 0$) and with values of the control command k_a different than zero. In all cases, the tank current, i_T , is practically unchanged, but slight variations in the v_a waveform cause an imbalance in the battery module currents. It can be seen that the sign and value of k_a controls the battery current imbalance. In Fig. 19(b), the closed-loop control is activated but restricted to operate only with the reactive power ($sp_a = 0$) and with values of the control command k_a different than zero. It can be seen that the sign and value of k_a again controls the battery current imbalance.

As the active power and reactive power in this example have the same magnitude, the active control and the reactive control create the same difference in battery module currents for the same k_a value. Finally, Fig. 19(c) shows the more effective performance achieved with the complete control, taking advantage of both the active and reactive power.

Fig. 20 presents the results obtained using the switching-cycle-average model during a complete discharge cycle of the

battery bank with a constant current of 0.65 C, for the particular case where the SoCs of each pair of battery modules in each side are initially unbalanced. At the beginning of the simulation, battery modules A1 and A2 are at 70% and 100% SoC respectively, while modules B1 and B2 are at 80% and 90% SoC, respectively. The converter is operated so that side-A modules supply to the load the same amount of power than side-B modules. Fig. 16 illustrates the power flow during the initial phase of the simulation. Each side-A module delivers a different amount of power to the power converter as a consequence of the negative control command k_a , leading to a positive neutral point current i_{2a} and unequal average battery currents I_{A2} and I_{A1} , as shown in Fig. 20. Besides, each side-B module receives a different amount of power from the power converter as a consequence of the positive control command k_b . In other words, the control manages to effectively balance the SoC of each module along the discharge cycle, by simply properly adjusting the portion of power delivered by each side-A battery module and adjusting the portion of power received by each side-B battery module. With this approach, each battery bank on each side can achieve SoC balance by means of its independent balancing control, concurrently with providing the power required by the load. The power delivered to the load remains unaffected by the balancing process.

FIGURE 18. Simulation results under a three-level system ($n_a = n_b = 3$). Control disabled, $k_a = 0$. Modulation index $m_a = m_b = 0.9$. Phase shift $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

FIGURE 19. Simulation results under a three-level system and different control configurations. Axes units: [A] and [V]. Modulation index $m_a = m_b = 0.9$. Phase shift $\varphi = 90^\circ$. (a) Control based on active power. (b) Control based on reactive power. (c) Control based on both active and reactive power.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental setup shown in Fig. 21 implements the three-level system depicted by Fig. 12, realized as a hardware prototype. Two battery modules, described in Table 1, are connected in series configuration to implement the battery bank from side A. A 1.09 mF capacitor has been connected in parallel to each battery module. This capacitor is dimensioned to ensure that the battery current does not change its direction within the switching cycle; i.e., it does not absorb and deliver energy within the same switching cycle. Side-B battery bank is implemented in the same way. Fig. 22 shows the array of 6 by 3 isolated switching cells used to implement each of the two active NPC converter legs. The cells inside a dashed box are connected in parallel, and then these boxes are interconnected to form the full three-level leg. Each switching cell includes a 100 V metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistor, an isolated gate driver and a self-powered gate driver power supply (GDPS) [46]. The tank is implemented by a 94 μ H inductor and a 30 μ F capacitor. This tank presents a parasitic resistance of 10 m Ω . The load is a 20 Ω high-power resistor. Fig. 23 presents the battery module currents, i_{A1} and i_{A2} , along with their corresponding average values, I_{A1} and I_{A2} , under balanced conditions ($k_a = 0$). The waveforms show good correlation with the simulation results depicted in Fig. 18. Fig. 24 shows that when the control is enabled, the system is able to create a difference in the extracted battery currents with both the active and reactive power-based controls. The minor differences with reference to the simulation results shown in Fig. 19 can be

FIGURE 20. Simulation results under a three-level system and a full battery discharge cycle with an initial SoC imbalance in both side A and side B. Modulation index $m_a = m_b = 0.9$. Phase shift $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

FIGURE 21. Laboratory scaled-down experimental setup.

FIGURE 22. Switching cell array used to implement each active NPC leg.

FIGURE 23. Experimental results under a three-level system and $k_a = 0$. Modulation index $m_a = m_b = 0.9$. Phase shift $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

FIGURE 24. Experimental results under a three-level system and different control configurations. Modulation index $m_a = m_b = 0.9$. Phase shift $\varphi = 90^\circ$. (a) Control based on active power. (b) Control based on reactive power. (c) Control based on both active and reactive power.

attributed to inaccuracies in the measurements and variations in the dc-link voltages on sides A and B.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a novel hybrid battery energy storage system implemented with a multilevel neutral-point-clamped converter interfacing two heterogeneous battery banks. The proposed HBESS allows to utilize two different battery chemistries that, when used alone, can only inefficiently fulfill the system requirements at the expense of an excessive volume and weight. However, when combined, they can fulfill the system requirements with minimum size and weight.

The proposed solution is modular and scalable. Different HBESS at different voltage and current ratings can be built from two standard battery modules with different chemistries and one standard semiconductor device, reducing the cost thanks to economies of scale. The suitability and feasibility of the proposed approach have been verified both through simulation and experiments in the simplest three-level case.

The proposed system, through the applied operating principle, is able to control the bidirectional power flow between the two battery banks; i.e., the total amount of power that each bank is delivering or receiving. In parallel, the developed modulation and SoC balancing control guarantees the balance of the SoC of all battery modules in each battery bank, in a lossless manner, regardless of their possible different aging. It is also important to note that thanks to the type of modulation employed [45], the operation at more than three levels with a balanced switching-cycle average power delivered/received by each battery module is possible.

Present battery energy storage systems are limited by the capacity of the weakest module in the system. In the proposed system, the energy demand can be controlled on a per-module basis, so that the SoC of all modules remain always balanced, and also so that the energy extraction/injection in degraded or more aged battery modules can be reduced according to their state-of-health. This is especially relevant in second life applications, where the battery modules can feature different ageing or even come from different manufacturers.

Finally, the proposed HBESS is not limited to the parallel hybrid configuration, where the final voltage is that of one of the two battery banks, but it is also possible to obtain a HBESS with a series hybrid configuration, featuring a higher voltage.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank all the members of the Helios consortium for the enriching discussions regarding this work, which have significantly impacted the design of the present study. In particular, we would like to thank Dr. Lluís Trilla from the Catalonia Institute for Energy Research, Dr. Luis Romeral from Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Dr. Corneliu Barbu and Dr. Farshid Naseri from Aarhus University, and Dr. Markus Schweizer-Berberich from Vitesco Technologies GmbH.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Evro, B. A. Oni, and O. S. Tomomewo, "Global strategies for a low-carbon future: Lessons from the US, China, and EU's pursuit of carbon neutrality," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 461, p. 142635, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.142635.
- [2] "EU common transport policy: European parliament." [Online]. Available: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/123/common-transport-policy-overview>
- [3] T. Pereira, Y. Wei, Y. Pascal, H. A. Mantooth, and M. Liserre, "Self-Tuning Multiport Resonant DC/DC Converter Based on Actively-Controlled Inductors for Hybrid Storage System Integration," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, pp. 1–18, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2022.3232188.
- [4] H. Tu, H. Feng, S. Srdic, and S. Lukic, "Extreme fast charging of electric vehicles: A technology overview," *IEEE Trans. Transp. Electrification*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 861–878, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2019.2958709.
- [5] J. Becker, T. Nemeth, R. Wegmann, and D. U. Sauer, "Dimensioning and optimization of hybrid li-ion battery systems for EVs," *World Electr. Veh. J.*, vol. 9, no. 2, Art. no. 2, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.3390/wevj9020019.
- [6] F. Naseri, C. Barbu, and T. Sarikurt, "Optimal sizing of hybrid high-energy/high-power battery energy storage systems to improve battery cycle life and charging power in electric vehicle applications," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 55, p. 105768, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2022.105768.
- [7] H. Kim and S. Jung, "Battery hybridization for achieving both high power and high energy densities," *Int. J. Energy Res.*, vol. 42, no. 14, pp. 4383–4394, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1002/er.4178.
- [8] Z. Jiang and R. A. Dougal, "A compact digitally controlled fuel cell/battery hybrid power source," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 1094–1104, Jun. 2006, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2006.878324.
- [9] J. Dixon, I. Nakashima, E. F. Arcos, and M. Ortuzar, "Electric vehicle using a combination of ultracapacitors and zebra battery," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 943–949, Mar. 2010, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2009.2027920.
- [10] Z. Zheng, K. Wang, Y. Li, H. Liu, and F. Chang, "A modular-cascaded active-balanced storage system for electric transportation," in *Proc. IEEE Transp. Electrific. Conf. Expo.*, Jun. 2018, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/ITEC-AP.2018.8433292.
- [11] S. M. Lukic, S. G. Wirasingha, F. Rodriguez, J. Cao, and A. Emadi, "Power Management of an Ultracapacitor/Battery Hybrid Energy Storage System in an HEV," in *Proc. IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conf.*, Sep. 2006, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/VPPC.2006.364357.
- [12] N. Omar, J. Van Mierlo, B. Verbrugge, and P. Van den Bossche, "Power and life enhancement of battery-electrical double layer capacitor for hybrid electric and charge-depleting plug-in vehicle applications," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 55, no. 25, pp. 7524–7531, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.electacta.2010.03.039.
- [13] J. M. Blanes, R. Gutiérrez, A. Garrigós, J. L. Lizán, and J. M. Cuadrado, "Electric vehicle battery life extension using ultracapacitors and an FPGA controlled interleaved buck-boost converter," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 5940–5948, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2013.2255316.
- [14] N.-D. Nguyen, C. Yoon, and Y. I. Lee, "A Standalone Energy Management System of Battery/Supercapacitor Hybrid Energy Storage System for Electric Vehicles Using Model Predictive Control," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 70, no. 5, pp. 5104–5114, May 2023, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2022.3186369.
- [15] Q. Zhang and G. Li, "Experimental Study on a Semi-Active Battery-Supercapacitor Hybrid Energy Storage System for Electric Vehicle Application," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 1014–1021, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2019.2912425.
- [16] Y.-L. Lee, C.-H. Lin, C.-H. Chang, H.-D. Liu, and C.-C. Chen, "A Novel Hybrid Energy Storage System With an Adaptive Digital Filter-Based Energy Management Strategy for Electric Vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Transp. Electrification*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 5131–5142, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2023.3320817.

- [17] R. Ma, J. Song, Y. Zhang, H. Zhang, and M. Yuan, "Lifetime-optimized Energy Management Strategy for Fuel Cell Unmanned Aircraft Vehicle Hybrid Power System," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, pp. 1–9, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2022.3206687.
- [18] C. Sun, S. Q. Ali, G. Joos, and F. Bouffard, "Design of Hybrid-Storage-Based Virtual Synchronous Machine With Energy Recovery Control Considering Energy Consumed in Inertial and Damping Support," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 2648–2666, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3111482.
- [19] I. Vecchiu, A. Etxeberria, H. Camblong, S. Baudoin, and S. Kreckelbergh, "Hybrid energy storage system with unique power electronic interface for microgrids," in *Proc. IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technol. Conf.*, Oct. 2013, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/ISGTEurope.2013.6695408.
- [20] W. Jiang, C. Zhu, C. Yang, L. Zhang, S. Xue, and W. Chen, "The active power control of cascaded multilevel converter based hybrid energy storage system," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 34, no. 8, pp. 8241–8253, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2882450.
- [21] W. Jiang et al., "Flexible Power Distribution Control in an Asymmetrical-Cascaded-Multilevel-Converter-Based Hybrid Energy Storage System," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 65, no. 8, pp. 6150–6159, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2787557.
- [22] W. Jiang, K. Ren, S. Xue, C. Yang, and Z. Xu, "Research on the Asymmetrical Multilevel Hybrid Energy Storage System Based on Hybrid Carrier Modulation," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 68, no. 2, pp. 1241–1251, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2020.2967723.
- [23] L. Maharjan, S. Inoue, H. Akagi, and J. Asakura, "State-of-charge (SoC)-balancing control of a battery energy storage system based on a cascade PWM converter," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 1628–1636, Jun. 2009, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2009.2014868.
- [24] N. Surulivel, A. C. Sunny, D. Dev, A. K. Samanta, and D. Debnath, "A Novel Four-Port Converter With All Bi-Directional Ports Having Common Ground for Photo-Voltaic Hybrid Energy Storage DC System," *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. II Express Briefs*, vol. 71, no. 10, pp. 4571–4575, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TCSII.2024.3396175.
- [25] S. Kurm and V. Agarwal, "Hybrid Energy Storage System Based on a Novel Reduced Rating Multi-Input Converter," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 11, pp. 12133–12142, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.2987833.
- [26] B. Xu et al., "A Bidirectional Integrated Equalizer Based on the Sepic-Zeta Converter for Hybrid Energy Storage System," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 37, no. 10, pp. 12659–12668, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2022.3161984.
- [27] S. Busquets-Monge et al., "Multibattery-fed neutral-point-clamped DC-AC converter with SoC balancing control to maximize capacity utilization," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 67, no. 1, pp. 16–27, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2019.2896176.
- [28] "Helios EU H2020 Project." [Online]. Available: [Online]. Available: <https://www.helios-h2020project.eu/>
- [29] M. Vijeh, M. Rezanejad, E. Samadaei, and K. Bertilsson, "A general review of multilevel inverters based on main submodules: Structural point of view," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 9479–9502, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2890649.
- [30] M. J. Lain, J. Brandon, and E. Kendrick, "Design strategies for high power vs. high energy lithium ion cells," *Batteries*, vol. 5, no. 4, Art. no. 4, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.3390/batteries5040064.
- [31] W. Vermeer, G. R. Chandra Mouli, and P. Bauer, "A Comprehensive Review on the Characteristics and Modeling of Lithium-Ion Battery Aging," *IEEE Trans. Transp. Electrification*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 2205–2232, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TTE.2021.3138357.
- [32] S. Barcellona, S. Colnago, and L. Piegari, "Aging Effect on Lithium-Ion Battery Resistance Hysteresis," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 59, no. 4, pp. 4516–4527, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TIA.2023.3266307.
- [33] I. Spina, D. J. Rogers, G. Brando, E. Chatziz Nikolaou, and Y. P. Siwakoti, "Maximum Power per Ampere Modulation for Cascaded H-Bridge Converters," *IEEE J. Emerg. Sel. Top. Power Electron.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 264–275, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2021.3114005.
- [34] T. Kacetyl, J. Kacetyl, N. Tashakor, J. Fang, and S. M. Goetz, "Bandwidth-Increased Ripple-Mitigating Scheduling Algorithm for Dynamically Reconfigurable Batteries," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 104202–104214, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3204058.
- [35] M. Uno and K. Tanaka, "Influence of High-Frequency Charge-Discharge Cycling Induced by Cell Voltage Equalizers on the Life Performance of Lithium-Ion Cells," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 60, no. 4, pp. 1505–1515, May 2011, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2011.2127500.
- [36] M. J. Brand, M. H. Hofmann, S. S. Schuster, P. Keil, and A. Jossen, "The Influence of Current Ripples on the Lifetime of Lithium-Ion Batteries," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 11, pp. 10438–10445, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TVT.2018.2869982.
- [37] A. Ghassemi, A. F. Hollenkamp, P. Chakraborty Banerjee, and B. Bahrani, "Impact of high-amplitude alternating current on LiFePO4 battery life performance: Investigation of AC-preheating and microcycling effects," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 314, p. 118940, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.118940.
- [38] F. Chang, F. Roemer, and M. Lienkamp, "Influence of Current Ripples in Cascaded Multilevel Topologies on the Aging of Lithium Batteries," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 35, no. 11, pp. 11879–11890, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.2989145.
- [39] F. Savoye, P. Venet, M. Millet, and J. Groot, "Impact of Periodic Current Pulses on Li-Ion Battery Performance," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 59, no. 9, pp. 3481–3488, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2011.2172172.
- [40] A. Bessman, R. Soares, O. Wallmark, P. Svens, and G. Lindbergh, "Aging effects of AC harmonics on lithium-ion cells," *J. Energy Storage*, vol. 21, pp. 741–749, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.est.2018.12.016.
- [41] M. Usman Tahir, A. Sangwongwanich, D.-I. Stroe, and F. Blaabjerg, "Overview of multi-stage charging strategies for Li-ion batteries," *J. Energy Chem.*, vol. 84, pp. 228–241, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jechem.2023.05.023.
- [42] X. Huang et al., "Lithium-Ion Battery Lifetime Extension With Positive Pulsed Current Charging," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 484–492, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2023.3250850.
- [43] K. Hida, H. Hiranuma, and M. Uno, "DAB Converter Performing Internal AC Heating and Power Transfer Simultaneously for Lithium-Ion Battery in Electronic Vehicles," in *2023 IEEE Transportation Electrification Conference and Expo, Asia-Pacific (ITEC Asia-Pacific)*, Nov. 2023, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/ITECAsia-Pacific59272.2023.10372280.
- [44] M. U. Mutarraf, Y. Guan, L. Xu, C.-L. Su, J. C. Vasquez, and J. M. Guerrero, "Electric cars, ships, and their charging infrastructure – A comprehensive review," *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assess.*, vol. 52, p. 102177, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.seta.2022.102177.
- [45] S. Busquets-Monge, A. Filba-Martinez, S. Alepuz, and A. Calle-Prado, "A modulation strategy to operate multilevel multiphase diode-clamped and active-clamped DC-AC converters at low frequency modulation indices with dc-link capacitor voltage balance," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 32, no. 10, pp. 7521–7533, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2016.2636839.
- [46] M. Raya, O. Aviñó, S. Busquets-Monge, X. Perpiñá, M. Vellvehi, and X. Jordà, "Improvement of a self-powered gate driver power supply," in *2022 24th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications (EPE'22 ECCE Europe)*, Sep. 2022, pp. 1–11.

GABRIEL GARCIA-ROJAS (S'23) was born in Logroño, Spain. He received the B.S. degree in electronic engineering from the Universidad de la Rioja, Logroño, Spain, in 2012, and the M.S. degree in electronic engineering from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain, in 2015.

From 2015 to 2021, he worked as electronics engineer for Sakma Electronica Industrial S.A.U. In 2021, he joined the Power Electronics Research Group at UPC, where he is currently pursuing his Ph.D. His research interests include multilevel converters for dc–dc conversion applications, power conversion in electric vehicles, and hybrid battery systems.

SERGIO BUSQUETS-MONGE (SM'11) was born in Barcelona, Spain. He received the M.S. degree in electrical engineering and the Ph.D. degree in electronic engineering from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, in 1999 and 2006, respectively, and the M.S. degree in electrical engineering from Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, VA, USA, in 2001.

From 2001 to 2002, he was with Crown Audio, Inc. In 2005, he was awarded an Assistant Professor position with the Electronic Engineering Department, UPC. He was promoted to Associate Professor in 2007. Since 2023, he is Full Professor. In 2009, he was a Visiting Scholar at the Center for Power Electronics Systems, VPI&SU, VA, USA, and the Institute of Energy Technology, Aalborg University, Denmark. His current research interests include modular and scalable power converter design based on multilevel neutral-point-clamped topologies and electric vehicles. He has published more than 100 journal and conference papers in the fields of power electronics and industrial electronics.

ALBER FILBA-MARTINEZ was born in Mataró, Spain. He received the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in electronic engineering from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain, in 2011 and 2017, respectively.

Since 2020 he is in a PostDoc tenure track at Catalonia Institute for Energy Research in Barcelona. From 2011 to 2020, he was a researcher in the Power Electronics Research Group, UPC, where he stills collaborates in some of the group's research lines. His research interests include multilevel converters for dc-dc conversion applications, power converters for electric vehicles, and fault tolerant power conversion.

TUREV SARIKURT was born in Izmir, Turkey. He received the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in electronic engineering from the Gebze Technical University, Kocaeli, Turkey (GTU) in 2010 and 2016, respectively.

He served as a research assistant from 2010 to 2016 and as a guest lecturer from 2020 to 2021 at the same institution. Since 2016, he has been a senior researcher in the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) working in various projects including EVs, satellites, and robots as battery management systems responsible. Since 2020, he has been working in Rail Transport Technologies Institute (TUBITAK RUTE) at the same institution on battery management systems and battery packaging for different applications.

SALVADOR ALEPUZ (SM'12) received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and electronic engineering from the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), Barcelona, Spain, in 1993 and 2004, respectively.

Since 1994, he has been Associate Professor at Tecnocampus, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Mataró (Barcelona) Spain. He has been visiting researcher at the Departamento de Electrónica, Universidad Técnica Federico Santa María, Chile, and the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department, Ryerson University, Toronto, Canada. His fields of interest are multilevel converters, ac power conversion and predictive control applied to power electronics converters.

JOSEP BORDONAU (M'89) received the M.S. (Hons.) and Ph.D. (Hons.) degrees in electrical engineering from UPC-BarcelonaTech, Barcelona, Spain, in 1984 and 1990, respectively.

Since 1991, he has been an Associate Professor with the Electronic Engineering Department, UPC. He has been the Education Director in Spain and Portugal (2010-2017) and Master's School Director (2018-2019) with EIT InnoEnergy, Eindhoven, The Netherlands. His research interest is focused on multilevel converters, applied to renewable energies, energy management systems, distributed generation systems, smart grids, and electric/hybrid vehicles.